

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

KAU170, a promising short-duration rice variety resistant to brown planthopper (BPH)

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BPH was a serious problem in Kuttanad from 1973 to 1974. A hybridization program was started at RRS in 1976 to develop a BPH-resistant, short-duration variety using locally accepted modern varieties and BPH-resistant, tall varieties, such as Ptb 33 and ARC6650.

KAU170 from the cross ARC6650/Jaya performed well in trials for yield and pest resistance. KAU170 (IET9268) was released in 1990 as Makam (MO 9) for use during the three seasons in Kerala. It is a short-duration (110 d), dwarf (75-80 cm) variety with red kernels, short bold grains, resistance to BPH, and seed dormancy of 2 wk.

KAU170 performed well against locally accepted modern varieties in many field trials at numerous locations (see table). When screened for pests and diseases, it showed moderate resistance to sheath blight, sheath rot, stem borer, gall midge, and leafhopper. □

Performance of Makam in yield trials.

Trial and location	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Makam	Check variety ^a
RRS field trial, Moncompu, 1983-84	5.6	4.9
Multilocation trial, 1983 (12 locations)	3.7	3.4
Multilocation trial, 1984 (10 locations)	6.1	5.4
All India Coordinated trials Brown Planthopper Resistant Variety Trial (BPHRVT), 1988 (11 locations)	4.2	3.3
Farm trials, 1987-88 (10 locations)	3.6	2.7

^aJyothi at RRS, Moncompu, multilocation and farm trials, and MR1523 for BPHRVT.

Performance of Mukthi (CTH1) in coastal Karnataka, India

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The coastal zone of Karnataka is a narrow strip of land lying between the Arabian Sea on the west and the Western Ghats on the east. Rice is cultivated on about 0.2 million ha during three cropping seasons. Rainfall averages around 4,000 mm, the majority of which falls during kharif (Jun-Sep) when mostly rainfed rice is grown. Rice is an irrigated crop during winter (Oct-Jan).

Mukthi is a red-kerneled, high-yielding variety with cold tolerance and blast resistance recommended for southern Karnataka. It is well-suited to winter. Its performance in the coastal zone has been studied during rabi (dry season) under irrigated conditions in lowland farming situations.

In field trials at the Regional Research Station, Brahmavar, and the Agricultural Research Station, Kankanady, during 1989-90 and 1990-91, Mukthi consistently yielded 16% more than the local check Shakti, a

Table 1. Yield of Mukthi (CTH1) in coastal Karnataka, India.

Location	Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Mukthi	Check (Shakti)
Regional Research Station, Brahmavar, 1989-90, 1990-91	Red rice varietal trial	4.1	3.2
	Blast tolerance varietal trial	3.8	3.6
	Mid-duration varietal trial	5.2	4.9
Agricultural Research Station, Kankanady RRS, Brahmavar, 1990-91	Uniform varietal trial	4.1	3.6
	Demonstration plot	3.8	3.2
	Mean	4.2	3.7

high-yielding, recommended variety for the zone (Table 1). Mukthi also resisted diseases better than Shakti (Table 2).

Mukthi is potentially suitable for the rabi crop of the coastal region of Karnataka. □

Table 2. Reaction^a of Mukthi (CTH1) to diseases in coastal Karnataka.^b

Variety	Leaf spot ^b	Leaf blast ^b	Neck blast (%)
Mukthi	3.4	2.3	1.7
Shakti	3.9	2.7	3.2

^aMean of 4 trials. ^bScored with the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) on a scale of 0.9.

Remya—a new brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant, medium-duration variety from Kerala

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BPH is a threat to rice production in Kerala, especially in Kuttanad, which is a unique delta area with 52,000 ha of riceland, 0.5-2.0 m below sea level. Wet

season (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr) rice harvest coincides with the monsoon. Rice grains often germinate on the panicle before harvest. BPH has become endemic because of the warm, humid conditions. Kuttanad farmers use modern varieties, none of which have seed dormancy and BPH resistance.

Remya (MO 10)—culture KAU126 (IET9266), derived from the cross Jaya/Ptb 33—was released by RRS in 1990. Remya is a medium-duration (120 d), BPH-resistant variety with seed dormancy of up to 1 mo. It has red